

ASSOCIATION OF THE CHEK2 1100DEL C GENETIC VARIANT WITH IMMUNOHISTOCHEMICAL MARKERS IN BREAST CANCER.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17449370>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 23rd October 2025

Accepted: 24th October 2025

Online: 25th October 2025

KEYWORDS

CHEK2 gene, *1100delC* polymorphism, breast cancer, ER, PR, Her2/neu, Ki67, proliferation, genetic association.

ABSTRACT

The CHEK2 gene plays a crucial role in cell cycle checkpoint control mechanisms that respond to DNA damage. This study investigated the association between the CHEK2 1100delC polymorphism and immunohistochemical markers (ER, PR, Her2/neu, Ki67) in breast cancer (BC). The findings suggest that the CHEK2 1100delC polymorphism with the C/G genotype may increase the likelihood of association with higher proliferation levels, as indicated by Ki67 expression.

Introduction: Among the 200 patients constituting the main study group, 196 (98%) carried the normal *CHEK2* 1100delC C/C genotype, while 4 (2%) had the C/G heterozygous genotype; no cases with the homozygous mutant G/G genotype were detected. Among the 196 C/C genotype carriers, estrogen receptor (ER) expression was positive in 62.2% and negative in 37.8% of cases, indicating correspondingly effective and ineffective responses to hormone therapy. In the four patients with the C/G genotype, ER expression was evenly distributed (50% positive, 50% negative), suggesting no significant advantage in hormone therapy responsiveness. A similar trend was observed for the progesterone receptor (PR) marker: 57.6% of C/C genotype carriers showed positive results and 42.4% negative, whereas in C/G carriers, the ratio was 50% to 50%. Analysis of the Her2/neu marker revealed positive results in 28.1% and negative in 71.9% of C/C carriers, while among C/G carriers, the respective rates were 25% and 75%. Based on these findings, targeted therapy was found to be effective in 28.1% of C/C and 25% of C/G genotype carriers.

A more pronounced difference was observed for the Ki67 marker. Among the 196 patients with the C/C genotype, 83.7% showed a high proliferation index (>15%), while 16.3% had a low index (<15%). Among C/G carriers, these values were 75% and 25%, respectively. This finding indicates a potential biological association between the C/G genotype and higher proliferative activity. Statistical analyses demonstrated that for ER (C/C: 62.2%; C/G: 50%; OR = 1.65; RR = 1.24), PR (C/C: 57.7%; C/G: 50%; OR = 1.36; RR = 1.15), and Her2/neu (C/C: 28.1%; C/G: 25%; OR = 1.17; RR = 1.12), no significant differences were found between genotypes. However, for Ki67, the odds ratio (OR = 1.71) and relative risk (RR = 1.12) did not exclude the possibility of an increased proliferative index associated with the C/G genotype (Table 1).

Table 1.

Association of the *chk2* 1100delc polymorphism with immunohistochemical markers (ER, PR, Her2/neu, Ki67).

genotype	n	ER		PR		Her2/neu		Ki67	
		+	-	+	-	+	-	>15%	<15%
C/C	196	122 (62,2%)	74 (37,8%)	113 (57,6%)	83 (42,4%)	55 (28,1%)	141 (71,9%)	164 (83,7%)	32 (16,3%)
C/G	4	2 (50%)	2 (50%)	2 (50)	2 (50%)	1 (25%)	3 (75%)	3 (75%)	1 (25%)
total	200	124 (62,2%)	76 (38,2%)	115 (57,5%)	85 (42,5%)	56 (28%)	144 (72%)	167 (83,5%)	33 (16,5%)

Note: “+” indicates a positive result; “-” indicates a negative result. For Ki67, values >15% are considered positive, and values <15% are considered negative. The homozygous G/G genotype of the CHEK2 1100delC polymorphism was not detected in either the main or control groups.

Conclusion: The obtained results suggest that the heterozygous C/G state of the CHEK2 1100delC polymorphism may increase the likelihood of association with the level of proliferation (Ki67). This indicates that CHEK2 genetic variants may serve as important molecular factors influencing the clinical course of breast cancer.